

THE IMPORTANCE OF THE MOTHER TONGUE SUBJECT IN SHAPING YOUTH SPEECH, LANGUAGE CULTURE, AND NATIONAL THINKING

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ABSTRACT

This article comprehensively examines the role of the mother tongue subject in shaping the speech of young people, its importance in teaching the norms of the literary language, and its functions in developing language culture and enhancing national thinking. In addition, the study analyzes the status of the mother tongue in social life under globalization, the condition of language culture in youth speech, and the issues of adhering to language norms in social networks. The educational and pedagogical significance of the mother tongue subject is illustrated through relevant examples.

In today's conditions of globalization and an information-driven society, the issue of language has become more relevant than ever. Language is the spirit of a nation, its historical memory, and the main foundation of its culture and thinking. In particular, the mother tongue subject serves as an important tool in shaping the speech, worldview, and national identity of the younger generation. Through the study of the mother tongue, young people learn the rich potential of language, master the norms of the literary language, and acquire the skills to express their thoughts clearly, fluently, and logically.

A person's thinking ability, level of reasoning, and culture of communication are directly related to their mother tongue. Therefore, the deep and systematic study of the mother tongue is considered one of the priority tasks of the education system. The development of society largely depends on the level of youth speech and thinking. An individual with well-developed speech and adherence to literary language norms becomes an active and competent specialist in society. For this reason, the importance of the mother tongue subject is not limited to linguistics alone but is also closely connected with moral and ethical education.

The mother tongue subject is one of the core disciplines in the education system, as it teaches students the structure of language, its rules, and patterns of development. This subject encompasses such branches as phonetics, lexicology, grammar, word formation, and stylistics. Through these components, students gain a deep understanding of both the form and meaning of linguistic units. As a result, their speech becomes richer, their vocabulary expands, and they develop the ability to adhere to the norms of the literary language.

Language and thinking are closely interconnected concepts. Human cognition is formed and developed through language, and the clarity and logical coherence of thought directly depend on the accuracy of speech. Activities in the mother tongue subject—such as working with texts, analyzing ideas, and drawing conclusions—help students develop independent and critical thinking skills. This, in turn, enhances their intellectual capacity.

Speech culture is the ability to use linguistic units correctly, appropriately, and effectively according to communicative purposes¹. Speech culture is closely related to grammatical writing, correct pronunciation, and adherence to grammatical norms. Through mother tongue classes, students acquire both the theoretical and practical aspects of speech culture, which enables them to communicate effectively not only in everyday life but also in academic and professional contexts.

Special attention is given to the development of both oral and written speech in mother tongue education. Tasks such as summaries, essays, reports, and text analysis help students learn to express their ideas clearly and accurately. While written speech enhances literacy, oral speech develops communication skills. Both competencies are essential for becoming a well-rounded individual in society.

Language embodies the historical memory and spiritual wealth of a nation. Through the mother tongue, national values, customs, and traditions are transmitted from one generation to another. Proverbs, sayings, and examples of oral folklore enrich young people's national thinking and foster a sense of patriotism. The mother tongue subject not only provides knowledge but also fulfills an educational function by cultivating respect for language, national pride, and cultured speech habits among students.

In the context of globalization, learning foreign languages is essential; however, this should not diminish attention to the mother tongue. Otherwise, violations of language norms may be observed in the speech of young people. Today, youth are highly active on social networks; therefore, adherence to literary language norms in the digital space has become an important issue within mother tongue education.

Norms of the literary language are the socially accepted, stable, and universally binding forms of the use of linguistic units². These norms ensure the purity, clarity, and comprehensibility of language. Teaching the norms of the literary language is one of the primary tasks of the mother tongue subject. These norms are classified into pronunciation (orthoepic), spelling (orthographic), grammatical, and stylistic norms. By mastering these norms, students develop into proficient and literate speakers.

In particular, adherence to orthographic and grammatical norms in written speech determines the quality of academic and official texts. Teaching spelling rules in mother tongue classes is therefore of great importance, as correct writing is a fundamental condition for clear expression of thought. Spelling errors can undermine the comprehensibility of speech.

Pronunciation culture also plays a significant role in oral communication. Correct pronunciation of words, appropriate use of stress, and attention to intonation are developed

¹ Yo'ldoshev M. Nutq madaniyati asoslari. — Toshkent, 2019. — 41–48-betlar.

² Begmatov E. Hozirgi o'zbek adabiy tili. — Toshkent: O'qituvchi, 2016. — 112–118-betlar.

through mother tongue education. These skills are especially important for students in public speaking and interpersonal communication.

Furthermore, special attention should be given to teaching and studying the spelling of proper nouns, including personal names and place names. Many neighborhoods, local communities, and streets are historically named after respected and influential individuals who founded, developed, owned, or contributed to the improvement and leadership of those places³.

The mother tongue subject serves as an important means of instilling both national and universal values in the minds of young people. Through language, a person's morality, etiquette, and worldview are shaped. Literary texts, wise sayings, and examples of classical literature enrich the spiritual world of youth. Issues of moral education therefore occupy a significant place within the mother tongue subject⁴. Studying the works of great writers such as Alisher Navoi, Abdulla Qodiriy, and Cho'lpon in mother tongue classes enhances students' aesthetic taste and strengthens their sense of national pride. Classical literature plays a significant role in shaping the intellectual development and worldview of young people⁵.

Love for the mother tongue is closely interconnected with love for the الوطن (motherland). The inclusion of themes such as الوطن (homeland), people, history, and culture in mother tongue education strengthens the patriotic feelings of young people. Through language, students come to understand the past and present development of their nation, which in turn increases their sense of responsibility toward society.

Today, certain issues can be observed in the speech of some young people, such as limited vocabulary, excessive use of foreign words, and incorrect use of dialects and jargon. These tendencies lead to violations of literary language norms. In addition, the widespread use of abbreviations and disregard for spelling rules on social networks contribute to a decline in the quality of written speech. The role of the mother tongue subject in addressing these problems is invaluable. Through activities such as working with texts, editing, and careful word choice, students improve their speech culture. Exercises aimed at analyzing and correcting speech errors, guided by the teacher, are of particular importance.

Fluent and accurate speech is essential for professionals in any field. Official documents, applications, reports, and academic articles require rpamotical accuracy and clarity. The speech skills developed in mother tongue education prepare students for their future professional activities. The official-administrative style is studied separately within the subject, enabling students to correctly draft and formalize documents used in professional settings.

In modern education, the use of interactive methods enhances the effectiveness of teaching the mother tongue. Techniques such as debates, clustering, and brainstorming

³ N.B. Xalilova. Antroponimlarning lisoniy tadqiqi xususida. Central asian academic journal of scientific research, issn:2181-2489/volume1/issue1/2021, B. 170.

⁴ Karimov I. Yuksak ma'naviyat — yengilmas kuch. — Toshkent: Ma'naviyat, 2008. — 34–39-betlar.

⁵ Navoiy A. Tanlangan asarlar. — Toshkent: G'afur G'ulom nomidagi nashriyot, 2017. — 56–60-betlar.

encourage active thinking among students. Multimedia tools, electronic textbooks, and online platforms make learning more engaging and efficient.

The competency-based approach plays a significant role in today's education system. Within mother tongue teaching, this approach ensures that students acquire not only theoretical knowledge but also practical communication skills. For example, competencies such as text construction, editing, and selecting appropriate words according to communicative situations are developed. This approach fosters independent thinking and the ability to justify one's point of view, thereby enhancing students' linguistic and intellectual potential.

The use of project-based learning in the mother tongue subject enhances students' creative thinking. For example, by preparing projects on topics such as "Errors in Youth Speech" and "Language Culture in Social Networks," students learn to analyze real-life problems. Creative tasks—such as writing essays, articles, and participating in debates—stimulate students' speech activity and encourage them to express their opinions freely.

The mother tongue subject is an important tool for shaping overall language culture in society. Grammatical and cultured speech ensures mutual understanding among members of society. In a society with a high level of language culture, communication becomes effective and constructive. The knowledge acquired in mother tongue education promotes adherence to literary language norms in mass media, educational institutions, and the broader social environment.

The mother tongue is also one of the key factors in developing national identity. Through language, a nation preserves its history, values, and culture. Deep study of the mother tongue strengthens the national consciousness of young people. Respect for language is, in essence, respect for the nation itself. Therefore, the importance of the mother tongue subject in social life is invaluable.

In conclusion, the mother tongue subject plays a crucial role in developing youth speech, fostering language culture, and enhancing national thinking. Through this subject, students master the norms of the literary language and acquire the ability to express their thoughts clearly and fluently. In the context of globalization, greater attention must be paid to the mother tongue, as it serves as the spiritual foundation of the nation and a key means of preserving national identity. Teaching the mother tongue using modern methods contributes to improving students' communicative competence and helps shape them into well-rounded and mature individuals.

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